

D3.2 Resilience Toolbox v1

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Flex4Res members of consortium

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HANS BERG GMBH&CO KG	HANS	https://www.berg-kg.de/de/
GOIMEK S COOP	GOI	https://www.goimek.com/es
SORALUCE S. COOP.	SOR	https://www.soraluce.com/en
EIT MANUFACTURING CENTRAL GGMBH	EITM	https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/
NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/
CONTACT SOFTWARE GMBH	CONT	https://contact-software.com/
A1 DIGITAL INTERNATIONAL GMBH	A1	https://www.a1.digital/
BEIA	BEIA	https://beia.be/
SAVVY DATA SYSTEMS SL	SAV	https://www.savvydatasystems.com/es/inicio
MONDRAGON CORPORACION COOPERATIVA SCOOP	MON	https://www.mondragon-corporation.com/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	TU Wien	http://www.ift.at/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	TUDa	https://www.ptw.tu-darmstadt.de/
UNIVERSITAET SIEGEN	USI	https://www.uni-siegen.de/start/
IDEKO S COOP	IDE	https://www.ideko.es/

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List of Abbreviations

Table 2 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
MTBF	Mean Time Between Failure
MTTR	Mean Time To Repair
SoF	Severity of Failure
RA	Resilience Assessment
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
RDM	Resilience Data Model
POC	Penalty Of Change
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service
GUI	Graphical User Interface
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MTBF	Mean Time Between Failures
MTTR	Mean Time To Repair
FMEA	Failure Mode and Effects Analysis
FTA	Fault Tree Analysis
BNs	Bayesian networks
DAGs	Directed acyclic graphs
LMD	laser metal deposition
SCRA	Supply Chain Resilience Assessment
SPRA	Supply Plan Resilience Assessment
FRA	Factory Resilience Assessment
SFRA	Shop-floor Resilience Assessment
RRA	Resource Resilience Assessment
SRRA	Resource Resilience Assessment
RSPRA	Resource-to-Shop-Floor Resilience Assessment

Executive summary

Deliverable 3.2 is a major step forward for the Flex4Res project as it introduces the Resilience Toolbox in its first form at the macro, meso, and micro levels. In this report the multifaceted activities undertaken during the first 18 months of the Flex4Res project are presented, outlining the corresponding outcomes in alignment with the project's overarching objectives. Providing an exhaustive breakdown of concepts across individual tasks and the description of the RA tools and data model, this report is the first outcome of the Flex4Res developments and advancements.

More specifically, the report covers the following aspects and achievements:

- Resilience Assessment approach: A general approach, including the methodology concept and the toolbox architecture.
- Resilience assessment data model: The Resilience Data Model to support the RA toolbox data exchange and interoperability.
- Resilience Assessment toolbox v1: A detailed description of the Resilience Assessments algorithms, methodologies and implementation architectures.
- Resilience Assessment toolbox next steps: The next steps and workplan for the Resilience Assessment toolbox v2, which will be delivered by M30.

The methodology employed in compiling this document is rooted in the active involvement of WP3 tasks leaders and Resilience Assessment (RA) tools technical providers, who not only spearheaded coordination efforts within their respective WPs but also gathered insights from task leaders, ensuring a holistic report of the Flex4Res Resilience Assessment toolbox v1 during the project's first half undertaken activities.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Resilience of production systems is now a vital factor in determining long-term performance and sustainability in today's dynamic and volatile global economy. Natural calamities, supply chains, manufacturing facilities, shop floors, and individual resources are all vulnerable, as demonstrated by the COVID-19 epidemic, geopolitical unpredictability, and natural disasters. In addition to impeding operational continuity, these disruptions significantly increase the risk to financial performance and competitiveness in the market. Thus, it is essential to create thorough resilience evaluation instruments that can measure and improve the overall robustness of production systems. Through a methodical evaluation of resilience, ranging from the macro-level of supply chains to the micro-level of individual resources, enterprises may detect possible vulnerabilities, initiate pre-emptive measures, and guarantee prompt recuperation from unforeseen disturbances. These technologies will enable firms to prosper in an environment marked by unpredictability and continual change, while also providing protection against future uncertainty. Resilience assessment investments are now a must for any forward-thinking business that wants to preserve operational excellence and achieve sustainable growth.

1.2 Work package objectives and description

Table 3 WP3 results

No.	Name	Description	Delivery date	Status	Leader
1	Resilience Data Model (RDM)	Task 3.1	M30	completed	PTW
2	Supply Chain Resilience Assessment (SCRA) tool	Task 3.2	M30	In progress	LMS
3	Supply Plan Resilience Assessment (SPRA) tool	Task 3.2	M30	In progress	LMS
4	Factory Resilience Assessment (FRA) tool	Task 3.2	M30	In progress	LMS
5	Shop-floor level resilience assessment tool 1 (SFRA1)	Task 3.3	M30	In progress	IFT
6	Shop-floor level resilience assessment tool 2 (SFRA1)	Task 3.3	M30	In progress	PTW
7	Resource Resilience Assessment (RRA) tool	Task 3.3	M30	In progress	USI
8	Smart Resource Resilience Assessment tool (SRRA)	Task 3.3	M30	In progress	USI
9	Resource-to-Shop-Floor Resilience Assessment (RSPRA) tool	Task 3.3	M30	In progress	IDE, SAV
10	Resilience assessment GUI	Task 3.2	M30	In progress	INTRA

Flex4Res aims at developing and deploying a comprehensive toolbox designed to assess the resilience capability of production systems across three distinct levels: micro, meso, and macro. The machinery and device level—local, on-site components essential to daily operations—are the focus of attention at the micro level. Reliability of individual equipment and devices must be guaranteed in order to keep up continuous production and prevent bottlenecks that could bring down the entire system. Production lines and production systems used by the entire organization are included in the meso level. This level deals with how different production units within a single company are interrelated. It makes sure that disturbances in one area don't affect other areas of the system, maintaining overall operational stability and efficiency. Lastly, the focus moves to the full value and supply chain network at the macro level. This larger view takes into account the network's resilience from suppliers of raw materials to final consumers, emphasizing the value of strong bonds and backup plans throughout the supply chain to fend against outside shocks and interruptions. WP3 is dedicated to the comprehensive implementation of the resilience assessment framework. In order to ensure thorough and accurate data gathering and analysis, T3.1 focuses on developing a solid data model that serves as the foundation for the assessment framework. The development of software applications that use this data model to offer useful insights and facilitate decision-making processes is the focus of tasks T3.2 and T3.3. Furthermore, WP3 incorporates new hardware-related data sources and action units, leveraging sophisticated sensors and actuators to collect data in real-time and facilitate responsive actions. The resilience assessment toolkit is made both forward-thinking and grounded in practical applications by this combination of cutting-edge technologies, offering a multifaceted, deep, and comprehensive approach to resilience. Through the implementation of an intricate structure through WP 3, and by addressing resilience at all three levels, Flex4Res is well-positioned to significantly improve production systems' resilience, making them resilient, flexible, and able to flourish in the face of uncertainty and disruption. The outcome results of WP3, as they are initially identified in this first RA toolbox v1 are presented in Table 3.

1.2.1 AAS implementation of resilience data model

To enable the cross-company usage of the digital resilience services that form the resilience assessment toolbox in tasks 3.2 and 3.3, a Resilience Data Model (RDM) is developed representing a form of the behavioural interoperability according to ISO/IEC 21823-1:2019-02. The most important requirements are:

1. interoperability and integrability with the information model of the AAS, OPC UA Companion Specifications and the Gaia-X Self-Description
2. scalability of the description of interrelationships in terms of static and dynamic relations between multiple products, processes and resources but also digital services
3. unified ontology with a vocabulary and related methods.

Thus, the following actions lead to a solution fulfilling the aforementioned requirements:

1. usage of RDF syntax with serialization format JSON-LD
2. a knowledge graph with a database as a semantic network
3. working in close collaboration with the organizations Mechanical Engineering Industry Association (VDMA) and Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA) to ensure a common understanding and cross-sector usability.

1.2.2 Resilience assessment for a production's system operational levels

In this task the Penalty Of Change (POC) method will be implemented as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) for assessing the resilience performance in short, mid and long terms on the supply chain and factory level. The generic interfaces for calculating POC will be defined and implemented (LMS) which specific instantiations for the SID pilot case will be implemented. The method requires input data regarding the

production capability of the value chain (defined in task 3.1) as well as estimates (e.g. in terms of market evolution) that have an impact on the performance of the value chain. Apart from the algorithmic method implementation a Graphical User Interface (GUI) will be developed as well as the proper data spaces connectors to offer the service over the data spaces framework (INTRA).

This task includes developing resilience assessment services and infrastructure on the shop-floor and resource (services, devices, components, and utilities) levels. Product, process, and resource models (task 3.1) will be integrated to evaluate the complexity of the overall shop-floor and assess the resilience of production in the context of process redundancy and manufacturability for specific product features and resource capabilities. Specifically for the resource level multiple integrations will be relevant to assess resilience: (1) an AAS resilience model (task 3.1). (2) For the latter sensors will be integrated into a forming die tool to evaluate the resilience in a forming process. A progressive compound forming tool is iteratively designed, sensor integrated, manufactured and tested at USI and IFT. The technical reconfiguration mechanisms will be integrated into the die along with the sensors, and both integrated into the AAS. The hardware will be created in order to collect data directly on a production machine and perform configurations on the spot through integrated actuators. The integration of sensors and actuators will be performed through the use of additive manufacturing technologies such as laser metal deposition.

1.3 Deliverable requirements

The WP3 activities and advancements are addressed in three deliverables; D3.1 was submitted in M12 and described the initial version of the data model for the resilience assessments levels, reporting the data points identified for each level (macro, meso and micro). The other two deliverables (D3.2 and D3.3) are two reports addressing the resilience assessment toolbox specifications. In this context, both D3.2 and D3.3 will describe the methodologies and implementation approaches for each tool inside the toolbox. D3.2 is the first version of this report, addressing the initial progress for the development of the RA toolbox (v1), as well as the data model implementation, until M18. In the last deliverable (D3.3, M30) the complete solutions of WP3 and the implemented RDM will be reported. The deliverables submission plan is presented in

Table 4 WP3 Deliverables

WP3 Deliverables				
Deliverable ID	Name	Leader	Due date	Status
D3.1	Resilience data model initial version	PTW	M12	Submitted
D3.2	Resilience toolbox v1	LMS	M18	Submitted
D3.3	Resilience toolbox v2	LMS	M30	Pending

2 Resilience Data Model v2

The Resilience Assessment Data Model encapsulates key data points relevant to various use cases. It requires interoperability and integration with the information models of AAS, OPC UA Companion Specifications, and Gaia-X Self-Description. Additionally, it must be scalable to describe static and dynamic interrelationships among multiple products, processes, resources, and digital services, while

maintaining a unified ontology with a standardized vocabulary and methods. The subsequent chapters will detail the Approach and Use Case Data Models.

2.1 Approach

Building upon the foundation established in Deliverable 3.1, our ongoing efforts involve obtaining updated models from the use cases and unifying these models to create a cohesive framework. This process includes integrating the resilience model into the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) and implementing these refined models into the pilot use case.

2.2 Resilience Data Model

Figure 1 shows a high-level view of the resilience data model. With only the submodel element collections (SMC) shown. Appendix 6.1 includes a description of each property in the resilience data model.

Figure 1 Overview of the resilience data model

Coming from the root of the data model, it is split into multiple parts necessary for resilience assessment. The three abstract classes supply chain, shopfloor and resources respectively describe the three level of resilience assessment in our project – macro, meso and micro. The SMC employee contains the details of the worker responsible on all levels and on all sites. Most importantly the SMC incidents describes all abnormalities that arise during production. Finally, the SMC ResilienceKPI involves the output of the resilience assessment.

2.2.1 Supply Chain- Macro level

The supply chain is divided into three components: logistics, market analysis, and production site. Logistics encompass all aspects of transportation. Market analysis addresses demand and supply fluctuations. The production site includes the characteristics of supply chain members, focusing on production costs and inventory levels. This section of the model forms the foundation for the resilience assessment of the supply chain in Chapter 3.2 and the penalty of change method detailed in Appendix 6.2.

2.2.2 Shopfloor – Meso level

The shop floor consists of the production plan, work order, and operations. To quantify resilience at the shop floor level, the primary inputs are times within the value stream, such as setup time and operation time. This section of the model underpins the resilience assessment of the shop floor, as discussed in Chapter 3.4, 3.5, and 3.7. It incorporates inputs from the VOE use cases (Appendix 6.4), GOI (Appendix 6.3), and the pre-pilot use case at PTW.

2.2.3 Resource – Micro level

The micro level is divided into three types of assets: the transport system, the storage system, and the general machine model. The key indicators in this model are the mean time to repair and the mean time before failure values. Additionally, it considers the routing of the transport system, the availability of free storage slots, and the operational status of the machines. This section forms the basis for the resilience assessment of the shop floor (Chapters 3.4, 3.5, and 3.7) and the resilience assessment at the resource level (Chapters 3.6). The primary inputs for this section were derived from the models used in the VOE use cases (Appendix 6.4), GOI (Appendix 6.3), and the pre-pilot use case at PTW.

2.2.4 Employee

The employee is an important factor on all levels of resilience assessment and is therefore considered as independent of the levels. Main characteristics are the competences and certificates but also the status.

2.2.5 Incidents

A main component of any resilience assessment is the documentation and modelling of incidents that occur during production, whether in the supply chain, on the shop floor, or with individual machines. An incident can be diagnosed based on its outcomes, described by the input from GOI (Appendix 6.3), or depicted through specific scenarios that have occurred or are simulated. These scenarios can then be incorporated using the POC approach detailed in Chapter 3.2.1 and 3.3.1. This SMC impacts all resilience assessment methods outlined in this project.

2.3 Conclusion

The developed resilience data model comprehensively encompasses all resilience assessment methods explored in Flex4Res and also serves as a foundational framework for assessment methods beyond the project. Its structure is designed to be extendable and adaptable to specific use cases. Among all the SMCs, the SMC incidents stand out as the most critical component for resilience assessment. At this stage, the first use cases data models implementations (see sections 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4) have set the guidelines to implement the general Resilience Data Model across all the use cases in WP5. The use cases data models complete implementation will be presented in D3.3 and will be used in the WP5 activities.

3 Resilience Toolbox v1

3.1 Flex4Res approach

The implementation approach in the Flex4Res project to assess resilience lies in the different production system levels: macro, meso, micro. Macro refers to the supply chain level, meso refers to factory and shop floor levels while micro refers to the resource level. By making this distinction, one production system can apply resilience assessment in different levels of their setup, trying to identify weak points and tackle issues from the correct point of view. While the RA tools are developed in the context of WP3,

in order to assess resilience most of the tools developed are part of a common pipeline with the reconfiguration tools developed in WP4. The resilience assessment methodologies are described in the next sections. In Figure 2 the architecture approach of the RA toolbox is presented.

Figure 2 Flex4Res Resilience Assessment Toolbox initial approach

3.2 Resilience assessment – supply chain

In this chapter the resilience assessment method for the supply chain level will be described. The goal of the assessment is to evaluate the behaviour of the supply chain system under different unexpected circumstances, before the application of a supply plan. The approach is twofold: 1) evaluate the supply chain system and 2) evaluate the supply plan. Thus, two initial implementations of the supply chain level resilience assessment are presented, in order to investigate the resilience level in these two aspects of the high level planification. Both implementations apply the Penalty of Change (POC) method (Alexopoluos et al. 2022)¹.

3.2.1 POC approach

The Penalty of Change (POC) is an evaluation metric that gives a rough estimation of how much the system under study will be affected, if some potential scenarios will happen. These scenarios are referring to outsourcing factors that are related with unpredicted events outside the company's environment. More specifically, the POC is the following:

$$PoC = \sum_{i=1}^D Pn(X_i)Pr(X_i)$$

Where D is the number of potential changes, X_i is the i-th potential change, $Pn(X_i)$ is the penalty (cost) of the i-th potential change and, $Pr(X_i)$ is the probability of the i-th potential change to occur. The formula for calculating the penalty of change given above can be seen as the expected value of the cost in the

event that a change takes place. Usually, the shift occurs as a result of an internal (such as a machine malfunction) or external excitation (such as adjustments to the required volume of product or products). If there is a shift in the market, such as an increase in demand, the system might also adjust to accommodate the new circumstances.

The goal is to evaluate how much the supply chain will be affected based on a predefined objective. Thus, the RA tool will apply potential changes to the system, and result to a penalty of a predefined objective.

The POC method gives an estimation of an objective function result change. To apply the POC method, certain parameters need to be defined:

- *Scenarios*: these are all the potential changes that want to be tested and result to a new objective value
- *Probabilities*: these are the probabilities of the scenarios to happen
- *Objective*: this is a predefined function related to the supply chain system
- *Penalty*: this is the change of the objective value from the baseline scenario

The penalty of change is the sum of all the penalties multiplied with the probability of each scenario to happen.

3.2.2 Implementation

The Resilience Assessment (RA) tools developed in this production level aim at evaluating the resilience of the supply chain system and the resilience of a supply plan. Either it can be manually triggered through the UI or when a supply plan is produced, a RA is conducted. Moreover, the RA tools for the supply chain level can be utilized to compare the resiliency levels of two supply plans. In both cases, the objective that will be used as reference to apply the POC method is the profit calculated from the macroplanning tool developed in WP4. The distinction in those two methodologies can be identified in the macroplanning optimization method; the macroplanning tool results to an optimized supply plan, given a certain period in time. In our case, this will be one year (12 months). The change in a variable of the system happens at a particular point in this 12 month period. The optimizer configuration for the supply chain RA solves the macroplanning problem with this information in hand. Thus, the resulted profit is optimized based on the assumption that at a particular point in time a change will happen. On the other hand, the optimizer configuration for the supply plan RA solves the problem for the same period (12 months) but has no prior knowledge of when the change will take place. Thus, the resulted objective function is closer to a real case, where the supply plan has already been developed and the change happens without notice.

From now on, the two different implementation methods will be referenced as follows:

1. Supply Chain Resilience Assessment (SCRA)
2. Supply Plan Resilience Assessment (SPRA)

Figure 3 RA tools for supply chain and supply plan

Both tools implement the POC method. The difference lies in the optimization configuration of the macroplanning tool applied to result to a predefined objective. The POC method is presented in the following section.

Scenarios

The scenarios represent the potential changes of the system variables. Firstly, the parameters that will change must be defined. In this case, two variables inherited from the macroplanning tool will be tested:

1. *Raw material price*: this represents the price of the raw material needed from a company, in order to produce their goods
2. *Product price*: this represents the price of the products produced and sold

Moreover, the manner that each variable under study changes should be also defined. Initially, this will be mapped to a normal distribution, and later this will be defined from a forecasting tool, based on historical data. The last parameter of a scenario is the probability of a particular change to happen. The probabilities of all the scenarios should add to 1.

Initially, the main variable under study is the scrap price (SCRA) and the product price change will be inserted in the SPRA development.

Objective

The objective function is used for the penalty calculation. In this case the objective is the profit of the macroplanning tool. Given a solution (baseline scenario), the RA tools will apply the scenarios and new objective values will be reached.

Penalty

The penalty is the loss in profit. It is the difference in profit (baseline_profit- scenario_profit). This value multiplied by the probability of the respective scenario to happen, results to a scenario penalty.

When all the above-mentioned parameters are defined, the POC is calculated and is used in order to decide if the supply chain (SCRA) or the supply plan (SCPRA) is resilient or not. As already mentioned, there are two algorithms applying the POC method and will distinguish the resilience assessment of the supply chain and supply plan.

Supply Chain Resilience Assessment (SCRA)

This implementation approach shows the resiliency level of a defined supply chain system. Having an optimal supply plan inherited from WP4 macroplanning tool, as well as the objective value, which is the profit, in order to apply the resilience assessment method, we need to define what-if scenarios. As already mentioned, those scenarios refer to changes on some variables that are critical for the supply plan optimization, such as the scrap price. This is very important for the supply plan, since it is closely related to the objective function, which is the profit. The scenarios have two parameters to be defined; the first is how a variable change and the second is what is the probability of the variable to change. In a supply plan, the scrap price is different for each month. Hence, we need to define various scenarios that deviate from the initial estimations for the scrap prices, based on which the optimal supply plan from the macroplanning tool resulted. By iterating the scrap and product prices in the data model retrieved from the macroplanning tool, we are able to change the optimization tool input regarding the scrap and product prices and send it to the macroplanning tool to calculate a new objective. When the new objective is calculated, it is stored along with the probability of the corresponding scenario to happen. By applying this iteratively, at the end of this flow we have a set of scenarios, with the profits and the probabilities of those to happen. The last step is to calculate the penalty of change, based on POC equation.

Supply Plan Resilience Assessment (SPRA)

This variation of the basic RA approach for the supply chain addresses the RA for the supply plan. The basic difference between the SCRA and SPRA is that the optimization of the supply plan in the first occasion happens from the first month, while the second approach applies optimization on the new variable changes from the month that these changes happen. To be clearer, we give an example. Having a supply plan for 12 months we need to check the resiliency level of both the supply chain system and the supply plan. For the SCRA, the optimization of the what-if supply plans happens from month 1 to month 12. In other words, we know beforehand when a change will happen, and we optimize based on this info. However, this is not what happens in reality, since there is no prior knowledge when a change happens, or the response time is not sufficient for optimization. Thus, the second approach, SPRA, applies optimization of the what if scenarios from the month that a change happens. If a change happens in month 4, for the first 3 months the supply plan to follow would be the initial, while for the rest 9 months until month 12 would be the new optimized supply plan. With this, we manage to evaluate if the supply plan that will be initially followed is resilient or not. The flow diagrams for both SCRA and SPRA algorithms can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4 SCRA and SPRA implementation flow diagram

3.2.2.1 Overview

The realization of the above-mentioned methodologies will be described in this section. Both the SCRA and SPRA tools are developed with JAVA as programming language, while both utilize the macroplanning tool developed in WP4. Moreover, some REST services have been developed for data exchange (Supply plan, WP4 solver, POC SaaS). The initial implementation architectures can be seen in Figure 5. During SCRA tool initialization, a baseline supply needs to be provided as input. This supply plan lies in a repo and was extracted with the WP4 macroplanning tool. The data model then is used for the RA scenarios and the macroplanning tool is iteratively triggered, in order to respond with the objective function, which will be used for the POC method. Lastly, when all scenarios have been performed and all objectives have been stored, the POC service is triggered through a POST request, and returns the POC value. A similar approach is followed for the SPRA tool, since the only difference lies in the data model provided as input for the macroplanning tool scenarios.

Figure 5 SCRA and SPRA tools implementation overview

3.2.2.2 Technical integration

The use case for the supply chain RA tools will be SID and the technical integration will be started in the next period, in the context of WP5 activities.

3.2.2.3 Validation

The use case for the supply chain RA tools will be SID and the tools validation is ongoing, with the proof-of-concept and finetuning actions to be finished before the technical integration.

3.3 Resilience assessment – factory

The Resilience Assessment Tool for the factory level aims to assess the resilience using the Penalty of Change (POC) methodology, as described in section 3.2.1. To apply POC effectively, scenarios, penalties, and probabilities must be defined specifically for the factory level. The subsequent section will offer detailed insights into the scenarios, probabilities, and penalties employed in developing the Resilience Assessment Tool for the factory level. Furthermore, it will outline the use case and practical implementation details. This tool was developed by LMS, working closely with Sidenor use case, in order to extract the types of scenarios, penalty and probabilities.

3.3.1 POC approach

The POC has been delineated in section 3.1.2; for more details, please refer to the corresponding subsection.

3.3.2 Implementation

The resilience assessment tool for the factory level, will be implemented in JAVA and is designed similarly to the supply chain RA tools. An overview of the implementation is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 6 FRA tool implementation flow diagram

3.3.2.1 Overview

To utilize the POC methodology for the resilience assessment tool at the factory level, the following components must be defined:

- Probabilities
- Penalty function
- and Scenarios (changes)

In a further analysis, each scenario is related with a probability and a penalty. For example let us assume that X_i is a scenario that was tested and the penalty function $P_n(X_i)$ results the penalty of this scenario. In order to compute the POC the probability $Pr(X_i)$ of this scenario to be occurred is needed as well.

In Figure 7 the flow diagram of the tool is presented, which aims to utilize a simulator to simulate various scenarios and in Figure 7 the implementation overview is presented. Additionally, a baseline scenario is required to compute the POC, representing a production schedule for a specific input. Furthermore, a set of scenarios needs to be defined to simulate them using the Production scheduler optimization tool. For each scenario, input modelling for the reconfiguration tool is necessary. Once the tool executes a scenario, it will produce a set of KPIs, such as resource utilization and makespan. In this modelling process, the makespan will be utilized to calculate the penalty.

Figure 7 FRA tool implementation overview

3.3.2.1.1 Scenarios

The scenarios of the factory level are related with the following types of changes:

- New orders with high priority: customers with high priority make a create a new order.
- Resource break downs: resources breakdown for a content time range.
- Raw material unavailability: simulate raw material unavailability.

The scenarios above vary based on the different use case that will be applied. Also changes in the input of the *Production scheduler optimisation tool* may need.

3.3.2.1.2 Penalty

The penalty function aims to define the way that the penalty is computed in the presented implementation. Additionally, the penalty function is the following for a given scenario X_i :

$$Pn(X_i) = Scenarion_{makespan}(X_i) - Baseline_{makespan}$$

3.3.2.1.3 Probabilities

The probability for each scenario can be determined in two ways:

1. If historical data is available, the probability can be calculated based on the frequency of occurrence of the event in the historical data.
2. Alternatively, the probability can be estimated based on the expertise and experience of industrial experts.

3.3.2.2 Technical integration

This tool designed and will be applied in the Sidenor 's plant in Thessaloniki. Its purpose is to evaluate the factory's resilience by considering scenarios derived from historical data, as described in subsection 3.3.2.1.1. The simulator utilized will be the *Production scheduler optimization tool* developed by LMS in WP4 under T4.3 (tools for meso level). The penalty function employed will be consistent with the one outlined in 3.3.2.1.2. As the tool is still under development, uniform distribution probabilities have been assigned to all scenarios, indicating an equal likelihood of occurrence for each scenario. The idea is that this tool will be used to assess is a production plan is resilience to a given set of scenarios that have high

probability to be occurred. The POC will be used from the planners as a KPI to assess the production plan, together with other KPIs as makespan, resource utilization, number of working shifts, etc.

3.3.2.3 Validation

The use case that will be validated with the tool is the Sidenor use case. Additionally, since the tool is still under development, it has not been integrated into the use case for validation yet.

3.4 Resilience assessment – shop floor

The objective is to calculate the resilience of the shopfloor i.e. the current planned and executed schedule.

Takes as input schedule of jobs on the machines, machine information (MTBF, MTTR) and a schedule solver. Outputs the resilience value i.e. severity of failure of the schedule and adds a severity of failure value to each of the scheduled tasks.

This method builds on an existing scheduling algorithm, in this case the one developed in WP4/T4.3.

3.4.1 Severity of failure approach

This approach is based on the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) to get to a probability of failure and the Mean Time To Repair (MTTR) to estimate the severity of failure in combination with an adapted schedule.

The assumption for this method is that only one failure occurs per sufficiently short period of time.

1. Calculate binomial failure probability for each machine:

The binomial failure probability for each machine is calculated based on the machine's Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) and the number of tasks assigned to that machine in the scheduling solution.

The concept of binomial probability arises from the binomial distribution, which models the number of failures (or successes) in a fixed number of independent Bernoulli trials (where each trial has the same probability of success).

In this context, we're considering each machine's reliability over a fixed time period. The probability of a machine failing within this time period can be calculated using the following formula:

$$P_{binomFail,m}(MTBF, T, n) = P_{fail,m} = \binom{n}{1} \times \frac{T}{MTBF} \times \left(1 - \frac{T}{MTBF}\right)^{n-1}$$

With:

P ... probability of failure

$MTBF$... Mean Time Between Failure

T ... Time period in which the failure may occur

n ... number of tasks assigned to machine m

2. For each scheduled task in the scheduled solution calculate the severity of failure value:

Each task in the scheduled solution could fail, therefore each of these tasks will be considered as a possible point of failure. To calculate the severity of failure of that specific task, the task is replaced with a repair period (Mean Time to Repair- $MTTR$) and the remaining tasks are rescheduled, the makespan of the new schedule with a repair period instead of the specific task

in relation to the original makespan time multiplied with the probability of failure of the assigned machine results in the severity value:

for each task i **in** schedule:

replace task with repair period ($MTTR$ - Mean Time to Repair)

reschedule remaining tasks -> new makespan time t , alternative schedule

calculate severity: $S_i = \frac{t_{failure}}{t_{optimal}} \times P_{fail,m}$

with:

S_i ... severity value failing task i

$t_{failure}$... total makespan time of rescheduled schedule with repair period.

$t_{optimal}$... optimal makespan time of original schedule

$P_{fail,m}$... probability of failure at the assigned machine

3. Sum all severities of failure values of the tasks to get SoF value of the schedule:

$$SoF = \sum_{i=0}^k S_i$$

With:

SoF ... severity of failure value of the schedule

k ... number of tasks in the schedule

S_i ... severity of failure of each task i

The goal is to have a low severity of failure (SoF) value.

3.4.2 Implementation

So far only implemented in a test/simulation environment separate from the VOE use case. Contact Elements for IoT will display and manage the orders, display the resilience value and the new schedule, also it will be used as the IoT platform to represent the AAS of the machines and manage their live data. The resilience assessment will be offered handled via the data space. Once service is consumed the algorithm will be deployed with docker directly over the edge and the payment will be handled by the data space, an access token will be used to verify that a transaction took place and activate the algorithm on the edge and compute the resilience value. The result will be sent through the data space.

Figure 8: Implementation diagram

3.4.2.1 Overview

The resilience assessment tool requires the static properties MTBF and MTTR from each machine-AAS, the schedule which should be assessed and a scheduler object (which is provided as a service).

To access the AAS properties the tool connects to the AAS registry asking for the URLs to connect to the required machines, which it uses then to access the properties of each machine-aas in their respective server.

The AAS registry server, listing the URLs of the individual AASs, is running in a docker container, as well as the individual machine-AAS servers representing the machines.

Figure 9 Overview and algorithm flow diagram of IFT Resilience Assessment

Figure 10: Detailed Overview of IFT Resilience Assessment

3.4.2.2 Technical integration

Not yet integrated in the use case, only in a test/simulation environment.

This tool designed and will be applied in a Voestalpine plant. Its purpose is to evaluate the factory's resilience by evaluation the severity of each task failing. The scheduler utilized will be the *shopfloor reconfiguration tool* developed by IFT in WP4 under T4.3 (tools for meso level). The evaluation function employed will be consistent with the one outlined in 3.4.1. The idea is that this tool will be used to assess if a production plan is resilient to disturbances like a machine breakdown. The SoF will be used from the planners as a KPI to assess the production plan, together with other KPIs as makespan, etc.

3.4.2.3 Validation

The use case that will be validated with the tool is the VOE use case. Additionally, since the tool is still under development, it has not been integrated into the use case for validation yet.

3.5 Resilience assessment – shop floor value stream

3.5.1 Value-stream approach

The value stream method is an established method for analysing and designing value streams. A value stream comprises the activities required to create a product from raw materials. The method developed is therefore intended to build on the established value stream method and extend the value stream analysis to include the evaluation of resilience. The approach pursued to achieve this goal is to carry out

the resilience assessment on the basis of risks. The first step is therefore the systematic identification of value stream risks, which is at the same time the focus of the research work to this date.

The result of a value stream analysis is the recording of the value stream in the representation of the value stream map with standardised symbols. In the first step of this research work, the value stream was broken down into so called value stream elements using the symbols on the value stream map. The value stream elements were then summarised into four categories. Generally valid risks for the individual categories of value stream elements were then systematically derived and summarised in diagnostic models.

During the application of the diagnostic models, the actual risks of a value stream element are concretised in an expert workshop based on the generally applicable risks. With the help of the diagnostic models, one value stream element after another can now be analysed for risks. The entire risk profile of the value stream can then be compiled from the risk profiles of the elements.

3.5.2 Implementation

The first practical applications took place at the CiP process learning factory at TU Darmstadt (Germany) and at the company Voestalpine in Kapfenberg (Austria).

3.5.2.1 Overview

The diagnostic models were applied to a milling and an assembly process in the CiP process learning factory and the actual risks of the two processes were identified in a workshop. In a second application, an exemplary sawing process from the Voestalpine use case was analysed for risks.

This revealed the risks to which the use case at Voestalpine is exposed. In a second step, a resilience assessment can now be carried out based on the risk identification and resilience-enhancing measures can then be derived and prioritised.

3.5.2.2 Technical integration and validation (use case)

So far, an initial exemplary application of the risk identification has been carried out in the Voestalpine use case. Technical integration has not yet taken place. Resilience assessment tool is still under development.

The research results are to be published in the paper "Identification of risks in value streams for resilience assessment- diagnostic models" as part of the conference CIRP CMS.

3.6 Resilience assessment – resource

The aim is to quantify and increase resilience at the resource level of a manufacturing machine. The following chapters will present the tools in development.

3.6.1 Integrated FMEA-FTA-Bayesian Networks

The objective is to evaluate the resilience level of the press machine based on the dimensions of anticipation, reliability, and robustness. To achieve this, it is essential to investigate and quantify the machine's vulnerabilities to internal and external failures and capabilities to cope with those failures

across the dimensions of resilience. An integrated approach combining Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), Fault Tree Analysis (FTA), and Bayesian networks is employed to model and analyze the press machine's resilience level, which will serve as input for reconfiguration planning (WP4).

FMEA is a systematic bottom-up approach used to identify potential failure modes, their consequences (effects), their likelihood of occurrence, and how easily they can be detected before causing problems (detectability). Experts are involved in the FMEA process to identify critical failure modes in the machine. Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) complements FMEA by employing a detailed top-down approach to investigate the critical failure modes identified in the FMEA. FTA deconstructs the event by identifying combinations of lower-level events (such as component failures and sensor malfunctions) that could logically lead to machine failure. It is used to determine the logical relationships between the failure modes and their effects. The results of the FTA are then converted into Bayesian network model to quantify resilience.

Bayesian networks (BNs) are graphical models that leverage Bayes' theorem to depict probabilistic cause-and-effect relationships between random variables. They are essentially directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) featuring nodes (variables) and arcs (edges) denoting probabilistic relationships among variables. Variables in BNs can take various forms, including Boolean states (true/false, yes/no), ranked values (low/medium/high), or continuous variables. Baye's theorem, on which BNs are founded, computes the posterior probability of the input data when given new data that has an input parameter set to a specific state. This approach enables reasoning in a logical and consistent way. Bayes theorem can be represented shown in eq. 1 :

$$P(\underline{A}|\underline{B}) = \frac{P(\underline{B}|\underline{A}) P(\underline{A})}{P(\underline{B})} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Here, P(A) is the prior (unconditional) probability of A, P(B) is the likelihood function of the probability of new data B given existing data A, P (B) is a marginal likelihood (evidence), and P(B|A) is the posterior probability of A, considering the observed B. with the use of Bayes rule and considering evidence, it is possible to update our beliefs about the variable A to a posterior belief . BNs can be used for representing the impact of evidence on existing data through probabilistic expressions describing the causal relationships among variables.

The converted Fault Tree (FT) into a Bayesian Network (BN) will be combined with resilience capabilities and dimensions of resilience to create a comprehensive model of machine resilience in the BN. The model is then populated by using machine learning to learn the parameters from historical data. Sensitivity analysis and inference, special features of BNs, are utilized to intelligently reconfigure the machine. The framework of the approach is depicted in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11: Resilience Measurement framework

3.6.2 Smart tool for resilience assessment

One of the goals is to support the determination of resilience through a new design of a forming tool. The new forming tool, called smart tool, is being developed for the assessment of resilience and the reconfiguration toolbox. The smart tool is intended to offer a new concept for individual stages in a large transfer tool. The integration of sensors is intended to support the evaluation of resilience. In addition, an alternative guidance concept for the active tooling is being tested with the Smart tool, which is intended to facilitate reconfiguration.

Several concepts are being pursued in the development of the sensor concept. The sensors should be able to monitor relevant process variables at individual stages and enable faults in the process to be detected. On the one hand, research is being conducted into the integration of glass fibers with the aid

of laser metal deposition (LMD). On the other hand, conventional ways for sensor technology are considered.

In this respect, optical fiber is embedded with laser metal deposition technology beneath sheet metal near functional surface. Since, the optical fiber are resistant to electromagnetic interference, capable for multi-sensing thus ideal to be used in harsh environment. With laser metal deposition it is possible to fabricate on existing surfaces. The principal test and optimization of process parameters is so far completed. Sensing capability of fibers after LMD is yet to be analyzed. Further, extending the results to the machine tools is also planned for future activities.

Figure 12 Embedded optical fiber

Additionally, together with Hans, IFT and USI, measurements were carried out with piezo-electric acceleration sensors on Hans Berg's large transfer die for the use of conventional sensors. It was investigated whether it is possible to recognise the occurrence of faults in the process through the transmission of structure-borne sound. For this purpose, the structure-borne noise was measured and characterised at various measuring points during operation without the occurrence of faults. Subsequently, faults, such as the introduction of notches on the belt (see Figure 13a), resulting in faulty components with scratches (see Figure 13b), were created artificially.

Figure 13: a) notches on input material (left) and b) scratches on final product (right)

The analysis of the measurement data by IFT has shown that the anomalies of the defects in the transfer die could not be reliably detected by the structure-borne sound, which is partly due to the mass of the components in the transfer die over which the sound is transmitted and generated. For this reason, the use of structure-borne sound sensors is not being pursued further.

The next steps for the use of conventional sensors for the smart tool are gas pressure sensors for the gas springs, the introduction of strain gauge and temperature sensors in the active forming tools and alternative options for monitoring the movement of the ejection plate in the transfer tool.

In order to reduce the effort involved in reconfiguring and setting up the active tools, a concept was pursued in which the guide, which ensures the co-centric alignment of the punch and die in deep-drawing and ironing tools, is located near the forming zone instead of being guided by the outer column frame. The following Figure 14a and Figure 14b show the CAD of a deep-drawing and ironing demonstrator, which is used to realize guiding near the forming zone and provides a comparison with the series process.

Figure 14: a) deep-drawing concept (left) and b) ironing concept (right)

The application and the development of the Smart tool run in parallel with the development of the resilience toolbox.

3.6.2 Implementation

Two developments were pursued for the development of the Smart Tool. Firstly, the integration of sensors and a flexible forming concept for the forming tool. the first implementation of the Smart tool takes place in the Pre-Pilot from Wp5. The application for collecting data for FMEA-FTA-Bayesian Networks is in its initial stages.

3.6.2.1 Overview

The need for reconfiguration in the press machine is triggered by actual breakdowns in the press, faults detected by sensors embedded in the die, and the measured level of resilience in the integrated methodology model. When actual breakdowns occur, the AI knowledge-based human-assisted system guides both skilled and unskilled operators to reconfigure the press intelligently. Similarly, when a fault is detected by the integrated sensor system, the AI system directs operators to efficiently reconfigure the press. Using a Bayesian network, the integrated resilience model measures resilience quarterly by updating model parameters with historical data. This triggers reconfiguration for predictive maintenance, where the AI knowledge-based system also plays a significant role. The synergy among the resilience assessment methods and the reconfiguration planning is depicted in the Figure 15.

Figure 15 Synergy between the resilience assessment and reconfiguration toolboxes

3.6.2.2 Technical integration

Not yet integrated in the use case, only in a test/simulation environment. Part of the development of the smart tool will be integrated into the use case. The focus of sensor integration is on stable conventional sensors that can be installed in the large transfer tool. The measures for using the Resilience Measurement Module are planned to be fully integrated.

3.6.2.3 Validation

Not yet integrated in the use case, only in a test/simulation environment.

3.7 Resilience assessment – resource-to-shop-floor

The objective is to improve the resilience of the shop floor at Goimek by anticipating or early detecting problems at machine or machining process level.

The resilience is defined as the ability to¹:

- Anticipate and consider actual or potential production disruptions
- Recognize their occurrence at an early stage and prevent their development
- Mitigate their intensity
- Cushion their damage
- Recover quickly from them
- Successfully adapt and learn from them

The method uses the application for production planning and reconfiguration developed in WP4, T4.3.

3.7.1 Risk / Severity of Failure approach

This approach is based on two factors:

- The evaluation of the risk of failure of the main components of the machine
- The detection of anomalies during the machining of repetitive parts.

1. Risk of failure

This factor is based on the concept of machine fingerprint. The main components to be monitored have been selected based on FMEA analysis of the milling machine.

The Fingerprint method consists of the obtention of information by performing a series of predefined machine movements in vacuum, without machining, called "self-diagnostic cycles", in order to identify its health or condition in an accurate and unique way.

The methodology for the use of the Fingerprints will be based on the systematic launch, on a regular basis, of the "self-diagnosis cycles". In such a way that each one uniquely identifies a state of health or condition over time. In this way, the first one is carried out at the start-up of the machine, being considered as

¹ [based on Wörner, J.D.; Schimdt, C.; Dachberger, S.; Kussel, G. (Hrsg.): Sicherheit, Resilienz und Nachhaltigkeit (acatech IMPULS). Deutsch Akademie der Technikwissenschaften, München 2022]

Fingerprint Pattern. Successive executions will be carried out on a periodic basis, with a weekly or monthly time interval, preferably.

The risk of failure of each component is evaluated assigning a value from 1 to 4, being 1 the lower level and 4 the highest risk of failure.

Different indicators are used for evaluating the risk of one component, the risk of failure of one component is calculated as the maximum risk associated to each of these indicators.

The three main components monitored are the spindle, axes and counterweight:

$$r_{spindle} = \max (r_1 , r_n)$$

$$r_{axes} = \max (r_1 , r_n)$$

$$r_{counterweight} = \max (r_1 , r_n)$$

Each component has a weight assigned to it. It is the MTTR of the component. It has been calculated based on historical records and is measured in hours.

The total risk of failure of the machine is a total factor obtained with the following formula:

$$R_{machine} = (MTTR_{spindle} * r_{spindle} + MTTR_{axes} * r_{axes} + MTTR_{counterweight} * r_{counterweight})$$

Figure 16 – Self-diagnosis cycles. Example of report (head condition)

2. Anomalies during machining process

The objective in this case is to detect anomalies in the machining process at an early stage and avoid costly failure development. It is applied for repetitive parts. The process fingerprint is a normality pattern based on several executions of the machining of the part. The process is constantly monitored and if the selected parameters exceed the limits established in the process fingerprint an alarm is sent to the

operator. The operator analyses the situation and evaluates the need for any repair of the part, he or she will evaluate the time needed to fix the problem, which is normally done by a new machining process of the part in the machine. This additional time of occupation of the machine is sent to the planner which can evaluate the planning in the production plan and propose alternatives if necessary.

Figure 17 Example of data acquired for anomaly detection in the machining process

3.7.2 Implementation

The resilience assessment tool will be developed in python and it will contain an UI to help the user to interact with it. The application will be dockerized, to enable the deployment and execution in other environments. So far, the tool is still under development.

Figure 18 - Implementation diagram for GOI Use Case

3.7.2.1 Overview

The resilience assessment tool is fed by the AAS of the machine that contains specific data for the resilience calculation. This data includes, among others, the result of the diagnosis cycles to calculate the risk of each critical component, together with the MTTR, and the repair time of the machine. The results of the resilience calculation are used by the planner that is developed in WP4 under T4.3.

Figure 19 - Overview of GOI Resilience Assessment

3.7.2.2 Technical integration

While the resilience assessment tool has not yet been integrated into the use case, the diagnosis cycles are already deployed and actively running in a pre-test environment and at the Goimek plant for the FS Machine. Currently, the data extraction process for anomaly analysis is also being fine-tuned.

3.7.2.3 Validation

The tool will be validated in the GOI use case, initially within a pre-pilot environment, and subsequently at GOIMEK facilities. As the tool is still in development, it has not yet been fully integrated into the validation use case.

3.8 Resilience assessment Graphical user interface

The Resilience assessment graphical user interface (GUI) is under T3.2, and INTRA is developing a GUI to present the different calculation of the Resilience assessment tools. This GUI will be integrated to the Resilience assessment for supply chain and Resilience assessment for factory level tools (both use the POC methodology), where both tools are developing by LMS. This GUI will be installed in the Sidenor use case. Additionally, you may find below some mockups from the GUI that INTRA designed.

Additionally, in Figure 20 are illustrated the mockups for the GUI. In detail, (a) is the log in page, (b) is the overview page where the user can see the created resilience assessment KPIs, (c), (d) and (e) are the steps that they user should following in order to create new resilience assessment measure, (f) is page for configuring the hierarchical level, methodologies and facilities that have been defined by the user, (g) presents the created scenarios and finally (h) and (i) are the pages where the user can create a new scenario. The tools developed using the [figma](#) tool. Furthermore, INTRA has already started the developments of the GUI.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 20: Resilience assessment GUI mockups

4 Next steps

4.1 Resilience data model

1. Unification of the Macro level POC-based resilience data model and the meso and micro level approach. The POC can be seen as a very generalized approach and therefore the existing meso and micro level model can be fit below the POC model
2. Talk together with the leaders of WP6 – standardization efforts are ongoing together with the IDTA to standardize the resilience data model as a submodel in the AAS
3. Together with the consortium partner Contact Software AG, the model is being currently implemented in the pilot use case of PTW in WP5.1.

4.2 Resilience Toolbox v1

Further development of the toolboxes and preparation for implementation.

4.2.1 Resilience assessment – supply chain

In the next period (M18-M30) further development on the supply chain tool and reconfiguration and finetuning actions will be performed. Validation of the correct functionality and reasonable first results will guide the finetuning activities, before the integration to SID.

4.2.2 Resilience assessment – factory

In the next period (M18-M30) further development on the factory tool and reconfiguration and finetuning actions will be performed. A first proof-of-concept needs to be reached, before validation of the correct functionality and reasonable first results is performed.

4.2.3 Resilience assessment – shop floor

Further develop the tool and find a solution to the slow calculation. Develop a new approach for the resilience assessment.

4.2.4 Resilience assessment – shop floor value stream

Further tool development and finetuning for the pre-pilot case.

4.2.5 Resilience assessment – resource

The next steps will include further activities related to sensor embedding, smart tool development, further experiments with the guidance concepts and resilience measurement model development. The optical sensor embedding process will be extended to include pre-pilot. The resilience measurement model will be developed using data collected from experts and historical data based on formats developed by USI. This model will then be trained, tested with datasets, and validated through expert elicitation.

4.2.6 Resilience assessment – resource-to-shop-floor

Refine the resilience methodology definition through testing in a pre-pilot environment to validate and fine-tune the tool. Optimize the data extraction for the anomaly analysis, and thoroughly test the integration with the resilience assessment tool. Additionally, finalize the development and integration of the tool with the Flex4res infrastructure (AAS, Flex4Res dataspace).

5 References

¹ Alexopoulos, Kosmas, Ioannis Anagiannis, Nikolaos Nikolakis, and George Chryssolouris. "A quantitative approach to resilience in manufacturing systems." *International Journal of Production Research* 60, no. 24 (2022): 7178-7193.

6 Appendix

6.1 Full Resilience Data Model Description

Figure 21 Overview of the resilience data model

6.1.1 Attributes of the resilience submodel instance

Table 5 Resilience Data Model attributes and description

SME type idShort	Description
[SMC] Employee	Models characteristics of the employee
[SMC] Incidents	Models characteristics of incidents, past or simulated
[SMC] Resources	Models characteristics of assets, namely, transport systems, storage systems, and machines
[SMC] Shopfloor	Models characteristics of the shopfloor, starting with the production plan, the working order and the operation
[SMC] Supply Chain	Models characteristics of the supply chain

6.1.2 Submodel Elements of the SMC Employee

Table 6 SMC Employee elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] employee_id	UID of an employee
[file] competences	The competence matrix of an employee
[file] certificates	The certificates matrix of an employee
[file] shiftplan	The shiftplan matrix of an employee
[range] status	The status of an employee [free, working, sick, leave, break]
[file] responsibilities	The responsibilities of an employee, e.g. machine, process

6.1.3 Submodel Elements of the SMC Incidents

Table 7 SMC Incidents elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] Incident_id	UID of incident
[ref] resources	Resources_id involved in the incident
[property] creation_date	Start date of incident
[property] finishing_date	Finish date of incident
[ref] fixer	Employee_id of fixing employee
[property] severity	Severity of incident
[property] failure_cost	Failure cost of incident
[ref] operator	Employee_id of operators during incidents
[range] status	Status of incident [solved, unsolved]
[property] due_date	Due date when incident is finished
[SMC] Scenario	Description of scenarios

[SMC] Variability	Description of scenario variables
[SMC] Diagnosis_Result	Description of results of diagnoses

6.1.4 Submodel Elements of SMC Diagnosis_Result

Table 8 SMC Diagnosis_Result elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] diagnosis_id	UID of diagnosis
[property] KPI	KPIs of diagnosis
[file] reports	Reports about the diagnosis

6.1.5 Submodel Elements of SMC Scenario

Table 9 SMC Scenario elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] scenario_id	UID of scenarios
[property] penalty	Penalty of Scenario
[property] penalty_description	Description of penalty
[property] scenario_probability	Probability of scenario
[property] scenario_master_plan	Master plan of scenario

6.1.6 Submodel Elements of SMC Variability

Table 10 SMC Variability elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] variable	description of variable
[property] statistical_variability	statistical variability of variable
[property] distribution	distribution of variable

6.1.7 Submodel Elements of SMC Shopfloor

Table 11 SMC Shopfloor elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[SMC] ProductionPlan	Contents of production plans

6.1.8 Submodell Elements of SMC Production_Plan

Table 12 SMC Production_Plan elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[SMC] Working_Ordner	List of working orders

6.1.9 Submodell Elements of SMC Working_Order

Table 13 SMC Working_Order elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] working_order_id	UID of working_order
[ref] incidences	incidences_id of incidents happening during working order
[property] status	status of working order
[SMC] Operation	List of operations needed for the working order

6.1.10 Submodell Elements of SMC Operation

Table 14 SMC Operation elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] operation_id	UID of operation
[property] setting_time	incidences_id of incidents happening during working order
[property] operation_time	Time needed for operation
[property] operation_type	Type of operation
[ref] incidences	incidences_id of incidents happening during operation

6.1.11 Submodell Elements of SMC Resources

Table 15 SMC Resources elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[SMC] Assets	General Description of Assets
[ref] incident	incidence_id of incident of a resource

6.1.12 Submodell Elements of SMC Assets

Table 16 SMC Assets elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] asset_id	UID of the asset
[property] mttr	Mean time to repair
[property] mtbf	Mean time before failure
[property] failure_rate	Failure rate of the asset
[property] repair_rate	Repair rate of asset
[SMC] Transport_System	Description of transport systems
[SMC] Material_Storage_System	Description of the storage systems
[SMC] Machine	Description of the machines

6.1.13 Submodel Elements of SMC Transport System

Table 17 SMC Transport System elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] transport_system_id	UID of transport system
[property] transport_time	Time of transport
[property] routing	Route of transport

6.1.14 Submodel Elements of SMC Material Storage System

Table 18 SMC Material Storage System elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] storage_id	UID of storage system
[property] available_slots	Number of available slots

6.1.15 Submodel Elements of SMC Machine

Table 19 SMC Machine elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] machine_id	UID of machine
[property] critical_components	List of critical components
[property] execution_state	Current execution state of machine
[property] tool_lifetime	Lifetime of current tool
[ref] machine_diagnosis	diagnosis_id of machine

6.1.16 Submodel Element of SMC Supply Chain

Table 20 SMC Supply Chain elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[SMC] Logistics	Description of logistics
[SMC] Market_analysis	Main metrics of the market
[SMC] Production_site	Main metrics of the production site
[ref] incident	incidence_id of incidents in the supply chain

6.1.17 Submodel Element of SMC Logistics

Table 21 SMC Logistics elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] transportation_id	UID of transportation

[property] transportation_capacity	Capacity of transportation
[property] transportation_cost	Cost of transportation

6.1.18 Submodel Element of SMC Market_analysis

Table 22 SMC Market_analysis elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] demand_quantity	Quantity of demand
[property] product_price	Price of product
[property] supply_market_capacity	Capacity of the supply market
[property] supply_market_price	Price at the supply market

6.1.19 Submodel Element of SMC Production_site

Table 23 SMC Production_site elements and description

SME type idShort	Description
[property] site_id	UID of production site
[property] productivity	Price of product
[property] operational_cost	Capacity of the supply market
[property] energy_cost	Price at the supply market
[property] inventory_capacity	Capacity of Inventory
[property] inventory_cost	Cost of inventory

6.2 Input Sidenor and LMS

Figure 22 Data points of supply chain and factory level resilience assessment (SID)

The model shown in Figure 22 presents the penalty of change data model utilized by Sidenor for resilience assessment. A detailed description of the supply chain and factory levels resilience assessment is presented in Table 24.

Table 24 Supply chain and factory levels resilience assessment data model description

AAS entity	Type	Description
Variability	SMC	This submodel collection consists of entities that describe the variables and the way that these variable are going to change during the resilience assessment. More than one variables can be included in the “Variability” model through the “Entry_ID” submodel collection
Entry_ID	SMC	This submodel collection serves as the overall description of a variable used for the resilience assessment method. It consists of a “Variable” reference, where a variable of the supply chain data model is referenced, a submodel collection “StatisticalVariables”, where the specific characteristics of the variable in use are described and a

		property “Distribution”, which provides info about the variable distribution.
Variable	Ref	This entity is a reference at a supply chain data model variable, indicating the parameter that is going to change for the resilience assessment
StatisticalVariables	SMC	This submodel collection consists of multiple “StatisticalVariable” submodel collections that describe the variable characteristics
StatisticalVariable	SMC	This submodel collection consists of the entities “name” and “value” that describe the variable specifics
Name	Prop	This property of a “StatisticalVariable” submodel collection describes the name of the variable parameter
Value	Prop	This property of a “StatisticalVariable” submodel collection gives the value of the variable parameter
Distribution	Prop	This property describes the distribution of the variable under study
Exploration	SMC	This submodel collection consists of “Scenario_ID” submodel collections and include scenarios that will be utilized for the resilience assessment
Scenario_ID	SMC	This submodel collection consists of the scenario IDs that will be used for the resilience assessment. Each collection consists of “Data” submodel collection, three properties namely “Penalty”, “PenaltyDescription” and “ScenarioProbability” and one reference “ScenarioMasterPlan”
Data	SMC	This submodel collection includes “Entry_ID” submodel collections, consisting of information related to the variables used in this scenario
Entry_ID	SMC	This submodel collection consists of information related to a variable used for the formulation of this scenario, such as “Variable” reference to the resilience assessment “Variability” submodel, “Probability” which is a property giving the change probability of the specific variable and “Value” property, which is the value that the related variable will change to.
Penalty	Prop	This property gives the penalty value of the scenario
PenaltyDescription	Prop	This property gives the penalty description of the scenario
ScenarioProbability	Prop	This property gives the probability of the scenario to happen
ScenarioMasterPlan	Ref	This is a reference to the master plan which is utilized for the resilience assessment
Quantification	SMC	This submodel collection consists of the metrics used to assess the resilience of the supply chain
PenaltyOfChange	Prop	This property gives the POC value, which is the metric of the resilience assessment following the POC method

6.3 Input Goimek

Figure 23 - GOI general data model

Table 25 illustrates the general data model of the GOIMEK use case. However, only the entities and properties highlighted are relevant for the resilience calculation.

The following table provides descriptions for each entity in the diagram:

Table 25 Resilience data model for shop-floor-to-resource level description (GOI)

Entity	Description
Production Plan	A production plan outlines the weekly production schedule, detailing how planning is executed across the shop. It specifies the working orders and operations to be carried out for each machine or working center at GOIMEK.
Working Order	A working order consists of a set of planned tasks associated with producing a specific article.
Article	An article is the part type to be produced. It contains a list of operations to be performed.
Incidences	In the case of a production incidence occurs, this is reported by the operator to the GOIMEK ERP. Incidents can be specific work order issues or any other problems that arise during the machining process.
Operator	Operator refers to an individual responsible for operating or managing equipment, machinery, or processes. Operators play a crucial role in ensuring smooth production.
Operations	An operation refers to a specific process performed on an article. For each article, working order phases to be executed on a machine or working center are established.
Machine	A machine or working centre is the place where different machining operations are performed (milling, grinding, etc.). Three main components are monitored in the machine: spindle, axes and counterweight, considered critical components.
Spindle Component	The machine tool spindle component contains a list of historical data of the self-diagnosis cycles executed. It also contains an extraction of specific KPIs (values acquired from the last executed cycle) which are used for the resilience calculation.
Axis Component	The axes component contains a list of historical data of the self-diagnosis cycles executed. It also contains an extraction of specific KPIs (values acquired from the last executed cycle) which are used for the resilience calculation.
Counterweight Component	The counterweight component contains a list of historical data of the self-diagnosis cycles executed. It also contains an extraction of specific KPIs (values acquired from the last executed cycle) which are used for the resilience calculation.
Diagnosis Result	This entity contains the results of the self-diagnosis cycles that are launched periodically (weekly or monthly time interval) in the machine to identify its health or condition

Diagnosis Result KPI	Extraction of data (KPI) of the machine's mechanical component in a particular moment, to identify its health or condition accurately and uniquely
Other Resilience Params	A set of parameters needed for the resilience assessment calculation (MTTR)

6.4 Input Voestalpine

Figure 24 VOE resilience data model

Figure 24 shows the resilience data model by VOE. In the following the classes are explained.

Rest Piece

The rest piece is the piece of material which will not be further processed and can go back to the storage place. We have one ID piece itself, so we can identify it for further process steps of other orders. We have different types of materials and type of quality, which is processed on the machine. The information is valuable perfect tool usage. The dimensions of the final production piece are useful find the right storage place. For a good logistics overview, we need to know the position of a piece.

Production Piece

The production piece is the piece of material which will be further processed or is already the final product for the customer. One order can have one or multiple pieces. So, we have one ID of the related order and one ID for the piece itself. We have different types of materials and type of quality, which is processed on the machine. The information is valuable perfect tool usage. The dimensions of the final production piece are useful find the right storage place. For a good logistics overview, we need to know the position of a piece.

Employee

The employee places a crucial role in the planning process, because the employee brings the material to the asset, set the machining parameters and takes it away. Especially for our use case, where we want to include the employee as a constraint for the planning process. Not all employees can work on all the machines, that's why we added the attributes for competences, certificates and responsibilities. The information regarding the shift plan adds the information of availability.

Material Storage System

The storage is the place where material is placed before, in between or after production steps. It's important to know where material is placed, so it can be brought to the asset. Storage systems have different capacity constraints, why we have included the attributes of max. Weight, max and minimum size, position, maximum place and free places.

Material Storage Place

The specific place is important to find each piece of material for any order. It could work for itself, when it is a place somewhere on the shopfloor or it is part of a bigger storage system. The place itself is a place where a piece is placed and therefore related to. We have the same constraints as for the storage system.

Saw

The saw is one asset, where the material is processed. The tool of a saw is a blade; therefore, we have added the constraints for the tool of the saw. Furthermore, we have added other constraints like max and min value for feed-, speed rate to have this knowledge for planning steps. The live information like status, downtime reason of usage status is important because it can influence the assessment for resilience or the rescheduling process.

Saw band

The saw band is the tool for the saw. After a certain time of usage, or a breakdown, the saw band needs to be changed. To match a saw with a saw band the information of length and height are needed. To increase the quality, it is also useful to know the tooth pitch and if the saw band is coated.

Transport system

The transport systems do help the employees to bring the material from the storage to the assets. There are two possible ways to bring the material to the asset. One way is, a system like a crane, which supports the employee. Another possible way would be a AGV's which brings the material for itself to the asset. All the systems do have constraints which needs to be checked, before a system can be planned for a type of transport. That's why we have added lots of different constraints to the system. Furthermore, a system needs to be identified with a name. Orders are placed or planned on a system and brings them to a target location.

Milling machine

The milling machine is one asset, where the material is processed. The tool of a milling machine is a milling cutter; therefore, we have added the constraints for the tool of the milling machine. Furthermore, we have added other constraints like max and min value for feed-, speed rate to have this knowledge for planning steps. The live information like status, downtime reason of usage status is important because it can influence the assessment for resilience or the rescheduling process.

Milling cutter

The milling cutter is the tool for the milling machine. After a certain time of usage, or a breakdown, the milling cutter needs to be changed. To match a milling machine with a milling cutter the information of diameter and height are needed. To increase the quality and plannability it is also useful to know the possible speed, count of teeth or after the usage the total cutting length.

Grinding machine

The grinding machine is one asset, where the material is processed. The tool of a grinding machine is a grinding tool; therefore, we have added the constraints for the tool of the grinding machine. Furthermore, we have added other constraints like the diameter for the steps of changing the tool. The live information like status, downtime reason of usage status is important because it can influence the assessment for resilience or the rescheduling process.

Grinding tool

The grinding tool is the tool for the grinding machine. After a certain time of usage, or a breakdown, the grinding tool needs to be changed. To match a grinding tool with a grinding machine the information of diameter and height are needed. To increase the quality and plannability it is also useful to know the possible speed, material or grain size are useful.